

ANALYSIS OF THE NEW ANTECEDENT OF SERVANT LEADERSHIP; A REVIEW

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Abstract

A leader can carry out Servant Leadership with a genuine passion to be at the forefront of service. Leading by example is also an important factor in the success of the Servant Leadership model. The objective of the study was to explore the psychological empowerment and servant leadership gap in the literature. This study used the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach to answer questions such as what is the empirical description of Servant Leadership antecedents for organizational working environment. This study obtained 41 articles with a search distribution with the synthesis of Academy Management with the keyword Servant Leadership. This article described Servant Leadership with the findings of three antecedents as Servant Leadership, Creativity Leadership, and Psychological Empowerment. The findings of the current study concluded servant leadership is a possible way for employees to find meaning in serving, and a sense of pride to have been part of the organization where they work, which is to work to achieve the overall vision and mission of an organization. So that makes employees a sense of enthusiasm and have effective relationships in their work and the ability to handle the demands of their work.

Keywords: Servant Leadership, Creativity Leadership, Psychological Empowerment, Employees Motivation

Introduction

The operating system of organizations has changed since the 21st century started and the market getting known as competition. Organizations started to focus on human capital as significant power similarly to investments that become one of the major keys to the surprising development and advancement of the European economy, O'Leary, et al., (2002). A number of findings have found a significant correlation between human capital and profitable organization. For achieving the high-performance category of "A players" create an environment where they bring innovation, smarter, initiative, resourcefulness, strategical development, visionary, passion, bring effective changes, quality, validation of teamwork, and discover novelty in finishing the target in minimum time and lowest in cost, (Smart, 1999; Scullion, & Collings, 2011). Employees with brilliant and intelligent mindsets in them leave a high inspiration in achieving organizational performance in any sort of working condition by making strategies on daily basis by utilizing their skillful capabilities. Such brilliant employees hold leadership qualities in respect of improving organizational working skills. A leader always set a role in developing an encouraging environment that would be motivational for other talented people in an organization with their supportive behavior. In this regard, servant leadership is known as one of the significant styles of leadership. In academics, servant leadership becomes the center point of researchers, especially in the context of organizations

or companies. This leadership style highlights the strong relationship between authorities and employees that would be based on long-lasting relationships, (Stone et al., 2004; Liden et al., 2008).

Servant leadership continued to grow until the 1970s. Robert K. Greenleaf (1977) had the initiative to start a modern movement on this concept. Robert K. Greenleaf (1977) was the one who introduced the word servant leadership and the concept of “servant-leader” in his first essay which was later turned into a book. Robert K. Greenleaf also built a non-profit organization that focuses on servant leadership, namely the Greenleaf Center for Servant Leadership. Robert K. Greenleaf (1977) servant-leader begins with the natural desire that someone wants to serve, first, Sendjaya & Sarros, (2002). The development of leadership theory increasingly directs that there is implicit relativity in the form of leadership ethics and development that is associated with the morality of leadership based on the field of organization. Social exchange theory (Blau 1964), which has been used to explain how leaders influence positive work attitudes among their subordinates. Thus, Servant Leadership emerged as the development of theories related to the forms of morality, ethics, and virtue in the realm of public service. An organization forms a unified perception based on the nature and identification in terms of serving and solving an issue together, Broch, et al., (2020).

The theory of Servant Leadership was written by Greenleaf (1970) and has received full attention from several scientific publications as one of the theoretical reviews in identifying forms of leadership, especially from the perspective of government bureaucracy. Several scholars such as (DePree, 1989; Covey, 1992), and Wheatley & Kellner-Rogers, (1995) have similarities in conceptualizing Servant Leadership that leadership as a form of morality in life has slowed down the development of the specifics of Servant Leadership. The criticism raises that the dynamic theory of Servant Leadership is very difficult to operationalize because the majority of research underlies that leadership is only stagnant in the absence of specific measurement tools, Hughes, et al, (2018).

Attributes of Servant Leadership

The attributes of servant leadership’s ability to incorporate specific talent ideas including techniques and work arrangements. Servant leadership system to accept in the organization, quantify of scope and determine the main goals and capacity to complete important choices in organizational settings on leadership skills. Therefore, visionaries in Servant Leadership must have the ability to increase organizational success in achieving targets, which incorporate the techniques to be applied organization, additional items, and benefits, company overview, executive framework, and organizational formal and casual design, Bavik, A. (2019).

Servant Leadership, Creative Leadership, and Psychological Empowerment

On the ground of the “Motivational Approach” by Conger & Kanungo, (1988), Thomas & Velthouse, (1990) stated that four drives to evaluate an employee’s awareness of empowerment are; choice, impact, meaningfulness, and competence. According to Thomas & Velthouse, (1990), four derives explained a detailed analysis and calculation to enhance intrinsic motivation in an individual which leads to psychological empowerment. Conger (2004),

mentioned that motivation in empowerment can be intensified by encouraging employees for their personal abilities, power, and meaningful sense for achieving any target in the organization. According to Spreitzer, (1995) empowerment can be related to inner motivation by shaping the orientation of an employee and enlightening the working environment in achieving an employee's role.

Job enrichment and psychological empowerment have a deep connection with one another despite a part of its concept of multi-dimension empowerment increased in different ways for job enrichment, Lawler, (1992). Foremost, it is grounded on the hypothesis of an individual can be a vocalist in terms of swaying and forming activities of an organization. For instance, as per the first hypothesis or assumption of this theory, an employee can be more influential in his/her organization over his/her job in achieving targets, Spreitzer, (1996). Additionally, these four dimensions for empowerment can be regarded with an individual's perception such as "cognition of an individual foil further aims", "the character of job oriented", and "individual differences which are given by (Hackman & Oldham, 1980; Judge, & Klinger, 2012).

Over the last few years servant leadership quite interested in organizational sectors across the globe that specifies "servant leaders have the main character which is serving first to its employees", Hoch, et al., (2018). Empirical investigations have found high performance, job attitude, and employee results are interlinked with their leaders, and these investigations resulted in servant leadership having significant outcomes, (van Dierendonck 2011; Chan & Mak 2014; Chiniara & Bentein 2016; Newman et al. 2017). According to Newman, et al., (2017), nevertheless, academicians and scholars emphasize findings on the creativity of employees and servant leadership mainly, on the other way, researchers still have to find a consent association between creativity in employees and servant leadership. Indirectly servant leadership has a positive impact on the creativity of employees. In some instances, creativity in employees have seen in bringing improvement in the creativity of employees attached to their promotion under servant leadership, Neubert, et al., (2008). A study by Liden, et al. (2014), argued that creativity in employees is indirectly connected with the relationship between employees and servant leadership where a leader serves their employees and this serving behavior enhances organizational success along with employee creativity. Peculiarly, in the association between creativity and psychological empowerment, a series of studies in these recent days have found the connection between creativity in employees and servant leadership significantly positive, (Seibert, et al., 2011; Sun, et al., 2012; Liu, et al., 2019).

Conceptual Model

Research Question

The research question of this article was “Servant Leadership and psychological empowerment relatable in organizational leadership in modern industrials era” The focus of this article was to summarize hierarchically from above based on the history of the formation of Servant Leadership theory with a review as a form of discussion on theory development in identifying new research area sectors.

Methodology

The methodology for this study was based on previous studies' literature. The literature of the current study was taken from quantitative and qualitative research work that has been conducted by several scholars in recent years. The data was attained by searching journal articles of Taylor & Francis, Sage Journals, Science and Technology Index Indonesia (SINTA) Journals, Springers, ERIC Institute of Education Sciences, and published books, by accessing Google Scholar with keywords; Servant Leadership, Lacking in Leadership Creativity, Servant Leadership in relation with Psychological Empowerment, Lack of Leadership in Organization Sector. The procedure for improving the literature review is expected to be able to understand the components that add to the creation and implementation of Human Resources in mechanical, hierarchical, and market development.

Study selection process

Image. 1

Results and Discussion

Servant Leadership

The Basic Theory of Servant Leadership, written by Robert Greenleaf (1970), defines that leadership as based on the perception of service. A leader's basic instinct for conscientious service is to prioritize the needs of employees, recognize the honor and importance of value to others, and help others achieve common goals. The concept of Servant Leadership as a leadership model was developed to overcome organizational crises in support of a holistic view of customer-oriented and bureaucratic aspirations, Khan, et al., (2021).

Service-minded leaders need the training to achieve service and the doctrine that their choices are responsible for bureaucratic aspirations that influence the behavior of their members. In addition to influencing employee behavior, managers clearly manage to overcome complexity by setting rules through formal planning, designing tight organizational structures, and monitoring results. Leadership as an implementation in management science with guidance and services that are in harmony with interactions with the environment, Shemueli, et al., (2020). Servant Leadership is aimed at the leader as someone who has the power to serve and lead. More importantly, the two can be combined to reinforce each other. Therefore, the main feature that distinguishes Servant Leadership from other leadership models is that the desire to serve precedes the desire to lead. In addition, people with leadership qualities become leaders. The vision shown in Servant Leadership has a top priority to develop subordinates who add value to their customers but create customer satisfaction for sustainable success, Wang, et al., (2020).

Servant Leadership defined as a set of actions that motivate followers to achieve performance that exceeds basic expectations by changing their attitudes, beliefs, and values. Servant leadership is described as a process in which leaders act as role models, foster creativity,

provide inspirational motivation, and promise to support and guide their followers to achieve the overall vision and goals of the organization. In an organization within a company, leaders must be able to manage the resources available in the company. Therefore, the role of the leader is one of the most important things to encourage the progress of every employee so that it can benefit the company in Servant Leadership skills to motivate employees to be better than they can be, in other words, affect performance improvement, modulate motivation, inspire and influence rational behavior, purposeful ideas, Pan, (2021). Updates on assigned subordinates' self-confidence and self-confidence habits. Customer's personal interest. Second, Servant Leadership helps followers by sharing information, increasing vision, knowledge, skills, and efforts to increase employee capabilities to achieve creativity. Furthermore, accepting and promoting new ideas, but also sharing knowledge and encouraging followers to think from different angles when looking for solutions to their problems. Employees perceive that Servant Leadership behavior is associated with better employee performance, Zhang, et al., (2021).

The impact of Servant Leadership shows the impact of followers on being more creative and innovative in carrying out implementation activities and the importance of the results achieved by doing hard work, while exchanging ideas and finding solutions to meet the needs of their organization or business, Iqbal, et al., (2021). Servant Leadership helps followers by sharing information, and enhancing employees' vision, knowledge, skills, and learning efforts, thereby enhancing creativity and furthermore, not only accepting and promoting new ideas but also sharing knowledge and encouraging followers to think from different angles when looking for a solution, to a problem in their organization, Wang, et al., (2020).

Creativity in Servant Leadership

Cohesion Team

Ardakani (2012) reported a positive relationship between organizational justice and knowledge-sharing intentions in a firm, and Schaubroeck, et al., (2011) showed that servant leadership positively affects team performance through mediators of cognition-based trust and influence in leaders. Creativity Leadership or the nature of giving to employees is expected to make a clear demand for fulfillment and fulfillment of deficiencies in determining decisions, Mehmood, et al., (2021). The relationship between Creativity Leadership and Servant Leadership is a form of self-evaluation of quality results or self-esteem, Shemueli, et al., (2020).

Creativity Leadership is also a model of positive feelings by giving expression to the individual. Individual satisfaction is a valuable thing, so it can be expected to respect other individuals. Individual relationships with low Creativity Leadership are characterized by superiority with unstable feelings. This relates to often saving oneself in response to an issue. There are three aspects of Creativity Leadership, namely Team Cohesion, Emotional Intelligence, Job Satisfaction Social. Creativity Leadership relates to individuals, trusting the perspectives of other individuals. Significance in understanding and respecting other individuals by shaping social ethics into high social creativity leadership. Social Creativity Leadership will be opposite to feelings of worry with negative brand models towards other individuals. Individual

relationships with low Creativity Leadership are characterized by superiority with unstable feelings. This relates to often saving oneself in response to an issue. There are three aspects of Creativity Leadership, namely “Team Cohesion Emotional Intelligence, and Job Satisfaction Socially”. Creativity Leadership relates to individuals, trusting the perspectives of other individuals, Shahzad, et al., (2020).

Creative Leadership in Servant Leadership is a development that is defined as a form of assessment based on self-perception, namely the result of obligations and how appropriate it is in the position ridden by the individual. The emergence of a self-assessment as a form of good or bad action works in accordance with its conditions. Cognitive in Creative Leadership in services for Servant Leadership becomes an illustration in self-assessment, Jeon, & Choi, (2020).

Creativity Leadership in Servant Leadership is the result of a derivative of a social cognitive theory that answers how the individual's perspective in assessing himself. Components are generally associated with individual behavior, environment, and cognitive factors that have a high correlation. There is a classification that is broadly divided into two forms, namely Individuals who have high creativity tend to be selective and do all their obligations. Obligations such as heavy tasks will still be carried out even though they have high risks. The development of these activities and goals is a form of commitment to determining these goals. Achieving success and considering failure as an indication of a lack of harder effort and the need for skill improvement. It was doing so to make individuals in this group tend to be persistent and follow the procedures in each process. But the opposite happens, if it is considered low, it can be classified as individuals who doubt their ability to fulfill their obligations. Individuals who are classified as low in creativity leadership in Servant Leadership actually have high ideals but aspirational applications are low and often avoid things that tend to be failed. Beliefs that are felt to be incapable of fulfilling the desire to achieve achievement, are slow to improve, and when faced with failure will be pessimistic, Moreno, et al., (2021).

Creative Leadership in Servant Leadership is called as self-confidence in leadership creativity not only through constructive arguments on happening, but as Individual beliefs in individual's abilities are determinant by describing how individuals act, logical patterns, and emotional reactions in dealing with an issue. There are four factors that influence Creativity Leadership in an individual's Servant Leadership, among the other, determination of action is the first factor that becomes the source of Creativity Leadership in an individual's Servant Leadership based on the level of actualization of a person's success in carrying out his obligations. Based on the selection of actions or decisions can affect a belief beyond the ability of individuals and activities that are adaptive. Individual judgments are based on abilities or actions that are logical or thought patterns when faced with obstacles. In problem-solving, individuals who tend to be high in being able to contribute failure to a lack of effort and ability to determine a good systematic. Furthermore, related to the results of logical patterns, individual psychological control, namely emotional reactions, must be balanced and able to respond to things that are positive in whatever form the issue is faced. Individuals who have high Creative Leadership in Servant Leadership are able to control their emotions to stay well. Coping

problem-solving strategies of an individual academically influential individual in the face of an obligation to determine each step that is estimated to be a problem-solving strategy, Shahzad, et al., (2021).

Individuals who tend to be high in being able to distribute failures to lack of effort and are able to determine good systematics. Furthermore, related to the results of logical patterns, individual psychological control, namely emotional reactions, must be balanced and able to respond to things that are positive in whatever form the issue is faced. Individuals who have high Creative Leadership in Servant Leadership are able to control their emotions to stay well. Coping or problem-solving strategies of an individual academically influential individual in the face of an obligation to determine each step that is estimated to be a problem-solving strategy. The only way to increase the effectiveness of the leader is to provide aspects of technical and conceptual skills, Lei, et al., (2021). As far as individual skills are concerned if the effectiveness of management activities and their impact on organizational performance is highly dependent on the sensitivity of leadership to the use of individual skills. These personal skills include the ability to understand individual and group behavior that contributes to organizational dynamics, the ability to modify behavior, the ability to understand and motivate, and the ability to understand process awareness. The ability to understand the relationship between leadership and the concept of political power in an organization, the ability to understand the sources of conflict and its negotiations, and the ability to build an ideal organizational culture, Khalil, et al., (2021).

Emotional Intelligence is a topic that has attracted much attention from business ethics researchers. Ethical Climate refers to a shared perception of the policies, practices, and procedures, both formal and informal, of an organization. Ethical climate is considered to be a type of organizational climate that reflects employees' perceptions of the ethical policies, practices and procedures of the organization. Although there is evidence that perceptions of organizational climate in an organization and subunits or work groups may have different climates, in this study, Emotional Intelligence was also a person's ability to receive, assess, manage, and control the emotions of oneself and others around him. In this case, emotion refers to the feeling of information about a relationship, Shafique, et al., (2020).

The dimensions of emotional intelligence (emotional intelligence) which measure self-awareness is where a person shows the condition of how well he knows the condition itself, his preferences, resources and intuition. This dimension is measured by 5 statement items, including self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Furthermore, the company's Emotional Intelligence determines its ethical values and behavior and influences the ethics of its employees. Therefore, ethically, employees tend to be more affected by the climate of the organization than the climate of their work group, Ahmad, et al., (2021). It was also found that the public has a low perception that the ethical standards of employees in sales are below average. An individual in the process of becoming an organizational leader is based on the idea that the individual will adapt to the social environment and be able to observe well, Imam, et al., (2020)

Leadership will have authority because it is able to occupy a position of relative status and is followed by members of the organization. Of course, this is subjective and needs to be a moral characteristic, Stoten, (2021). Leadership ethics is very influential in the corporate environment. An individual's greatest appeal to perceived leadership is power and status. Job Satisfaction for employees was a feeling that is desired in most organizations and is valued by staff. This is one of the key indicators of organizational success, Alonderiene, & Majauskaite, (2016). Organizational performance and effectiveness are influenced by organizational satisfaction and job satisfaction. However, even though all leaders have the same basic goals, it is still important to understand that they are different individuals. So no wonder all leaders have different ways, Paas, et al., (2021).

Servant Leadership has a strong influence both, directly and indirectly, ways or by being a median factor, influencing employees' job satisfaction (Fernandez, 2008; Aydin et al., 2013; Shaw & Newton, 2014; Yang, 2014; Schyns, et al., 2018). Di Schyns et al. (2009) research on the influence of organizational climate and organizational climate has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. Chang & Lee (2007) reveal how leadership together with organizational culture has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. According to Griffith (2004), leadership has a direct effect on job satisfaction, job satisfaction then directly affects staff turnover and school achievement progress. Yang (2014) argues that the effect of transformational leadership on job satisfaction is mediated by leadership trust.

Psychological Empowerment in Servant Leadership

Psychological empowerment is to build motivation from the four cognitions formed by the work environment, namely meaning, competence, self-determination, and impact. Psychological Empowerment is a process that begins with the interaction between the work environment and individual personality characteristics, and these environmental interactions form four cognitive empowerments, namely meaning, competence, self-determination, and impact which will ultimately motivate individual behavior. Based on this understanding, it can be concluded that psychological empowerment is a form of individual intrinsic motivation in the work environment which is formed from four cognitions to produce job satisfaction, psychological empowerment reflects an active work orientation, where individuals are able to determine their role in work, not just conveying ideas, Mehmood, et al., (2021). Dimensions of Psychological Empowerment are:

1. Meaning

Meaning is the suitability between one's job role needs and behavior, one's belief that he or she has the skills and abilities needed to perform a task or job well.

2. Self-Determination

Self-determination is a person's belief that the person has the freedom or autonomy and control over how to do their own work.

3. Competence

Competence is a person's belief or belief that he or she has the skills and abilities needed to perform a task or job well. a person's belief that he or she has the skills and abilities needed to perform a task or job well.

Psychological Empowerment that we. Current study findings based on SLR found psychological empowerment is needed to explore deeply in organizations, especially in the ASEAN region for Psychological Safety, Ethical Leadership, and Working Engagement. Psychological empowerment can be a resource and help individuals to bounce back from the adversity of the situation they are experiencing. In addition, individuals are diligent in work and can facilitate the hope that things will get better in the future. Psychological empowerment is useful in improving performance, individuals become more effective, increasing productivity, and motivation to work more, Ambad, et al., (2021). Thus, psychological empowerment provides many benefits to every individual who wants to change his life for the better which of course must be supported by the leadership, so that there are no obstacles in improving performance and productivity. Psychological empowerment can have an influence on individuals, organizations, and society.

In the development of Psychological Empowerment, there is a gap, namely Psychological Safety is a form of employee behavior consisting of work safety components, Chen, et al., (2020). Forms of work safety behavior are such as using work safety equipment and actively participating in work safety program activities in the organization. Neal & Griffin, (2000) also added that the concept of safety performance is employee behavior in the workplace related to organizational safety. Psychological Safety is also defined as a form of employee safety behavior at work which includes compliance and participation, Iqbal, et al., (2020). Compliance is defined as employee safety behavior at work and maintaining safety at work, participation is described as employee voluntary behavior to develop the organization's workplace safety. It can be concluded that Psychological Safety is a form of employee behavior at work that includes the prevention of work accidents by means of employee behavior that complies with established safety rules and procedures and voluntarily participates in improving work safety in the company. There are two aspects of Psychological Safety, namely Safety compliance is a safety behavior carried out by individuals in maintaining safety. In this case, safety compliance is an employee's safety compliance to maintain the safety applied in the work environment. These behaviors include following standard work safety procedures and wearing personal protective equipment at work. Safety Participation (participation) is an individual's behavior to participate in safety activities. Safety participation is safety participation that is seen in the behavior of employees in participating in safety activities that are applied in their work environment. These behaviors include voluntary participation in work safety activities, Wang, et al., (2020).

Factors that affect the occurrence of safety performance include the first factor is the ability of workers to observe the presence or absence of danger in the work location. Not all workers have the ability to recognize hazards in the work area. The ability to observe various kinds of hazards is very dependent on the knowledge or experience of workers in the area or the work

process they are doing. After workers are able to observe or identify potential hazards in the workplace, then workers must identify these hazards. Many workers are able to identify hazards in the workplace but are unable to identify the types of hazards that can occur. Although workers can already observe and recognize hazards, accidents can still occur if workers do not take the right decisions to prevent accidents. The ability to make the right decisions to avoid accidents is strongly influenced by culture, climate as well as safety behavior. If the culture, climate, and safety behavior that develops within the organization is a culture, climate, and risk behavior, workers will tend to take risks rather than avoid risks. The last factor that influences the occurrence of accidents is the ability to avoid hazards that have been identified, recognized, and decided to be avoided. Workers may have decided to avoid potential accidents that could occur, however, accidents can be avoided if the worker is able to avoid the hazard or risk appropriately, knows how to avoid the hazard, or knows how to do the job safely. The ability to avoid will be seen in the safe behavior of the worker in doing his job, Khalil, et al., (2021).

In identifying Psychological Empowerment, it is necessary to have an attachment to work so that the concept of work engagement becomes a supporter. A business management concept says that an employee who has high engagement is an employee who has full involvement and a high work spirit in his work as well as in matters relating to the company's activities in the long term. In other words, this definition of work engagement can refer to the involvement, satisfaction, and enthusiasm of employees at work. This work engagement also develops from various surrounding concepts such as motivation, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. Work engagement in a job can be conceptualized as members of the organization who carry out their roles in their work, Rahmadani, et al., (2020). Work and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during work. Employee engagement like that is needed to encourage employee morale Work Engagement. It is also explained as an interaction in two directions, namely between workers and those who provide work. Engaged workers can be characterized by covering several factors, including having a focus on motivation, job satisfaction, commitment, finding meaning in work, pride, and having a relationship with the overall vision and mission of an organization. More specifically, work engagement can be defined as motivation and becomes a center of positive thinking related to work which can be characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption, Khan, et al., (2021).

There is also another view of engagement as opposed to burnout. Engaged employees can have a passionate and effective relationship in their work and they feel they judge themselves as capable of handling the demands of the work they do that engagement and burnout are two opposite things regarding work-related well-being, with burnout representing a negative thing and engagement as a positive. Factors that affect work engagement include job demands (job demands), work resources (job resources), and personal resources (personal resources). On-the-job demands (job demands) lead to the physical, psychological, social, and organization of work that requires physical and/or psychological effort (cognitive or emotional) that is continuously associated with certain physiological or psychological expenses. Factors related to these work demands are working with excessive workload, emotional demands, emotional incompatibility, organizational change, high work pressure, unpleasant physical work environment, Rahmadani, et al., (2020).

Job resources can be interpreted as physical, social, or organizational aspects of work, which can reduce job demands that serve to achieve a work goal, and stimulate individual growth, learning, and development, Khalil, et al., (2021). The source of work has a positive relationship with work engagement. There are six factors included in the source of work, namely autonomy, performance feedback, social support, supervisory coaching, perceived organization support, and opportunities for development. Social support factors in work resources can be in the form of appreciation support. This award can be classified into two broader categories, namely extrinsic and intrinsic. In the extrinsic category, there are financial and interpersonal rewards. These financial rewards include salaries, wages, and benefits such as child care centers, fitness centers, and medical care. Interpersonal rewards in the form of status and recognition. While in the intrinsic category there is completion (completion), achievement (achievement), autonomy (autonomy), and personal growth (personal growth), Wang, et al., (2021).

Completion is the ability to be able to start and finish a job or project is important for some people. For them, it is a reward for themselves. This achievement is a self-appreciation that is obtained when someone achieves a challenging goal. In that sense, autonomy can result in the freedom to do what the employee considers best in a given situation. Whereas personal growth is in the form of opportunities and encouragement, given to the company to employees who are useful for employees to develop and grow, Griep, et al., (2022).

Conclusion and Limitations

There are three basics or antecedents as a result of this article, namely Servant Leadership, namely Creativity, and Psychological Empowerment. This aspect can be seen in the way a person is enthusiastic in dealing with his tasks by continuing to maintain his energy until the output stage. Serving which is a real component of behavior is always related to a person's internal attitude or attitude object, in this case, it can be seen when he involves himself as an individual with the behavior of someone who is dedicated to him so that when the individual carries out a task in his work, he will give all his potential with hopes and goals to get an award in self-actualization. While the third component is cognitive, is a component of information related to the attitude object and all information organized to respond to attitudes. In this component, it can be seen that if a person is already involved in his work, he will use a pattern of thinking to create a creative idea, trying to find innovation so that doing work feels light and enjoyable will provide an attitude of enthusiasm, dedication, and absorption, which can be analyzed applicative.

The conclusion that can be drawn from the description of the theory above regarding Servant Leadership is the attitude and behavior of a person in working by expressing himself totally physically, cognitively, affectively, and emotionally. Employees find meaning in serving, and a sense of pride to have been part of the organization where they work, which is to work to achieve the overall vision and mission of an organization. So that makes employees have a sense of enthusiasm and have effective relationships in their work and are able to handle the demands of their work. Servant Leadership can be exposed by carrying on other concepts as gap and research novelty, relating to a state of mind characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption.

A readiness to devote effort to one's work, an attempt to keep the spirit at work, and a tendency to keep trying in doing a task, difficulty, or failure. Dedication refers to a strong identification with one's work and includes feelings of enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, and challenge.

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